

Deliverable D4.7.

Report on ICT tools refinements after pilots validation

Report information

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BI	Business Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMT	Business Management tools
CDE	Common Data Environment
CDMP	Centralized Data Management Platform for DEQ
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DWH	Data Warehouse
ES	Expert System
ETL	Extract Transform Load
GA	Grant Agreement
HTTPS	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secured
ICT	Information and communication technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSA	Key Social Area
KTA	Key Technology Area
LoRa	Long Range
ML	Machine Learning
OS	Operating System
REE	Running Equipment Effectiveness
REST API	Representational State Transfer-API
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the continuous support and refinement activities conducted for the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) and related ICT tools, the AI services, the data warehouse and the Building Information System.

For the IQS, the objectives included ensuring system functionality, addressing technical issues, and implementing refinements to enhance performance and usability based on pilot site feedback. Key activities involved monitoring system components, resolving issues, and refining data integration processes. Significant achievements include the development of new connectors, improved data handling protocols, and optimized system components such as Azure cloud services and Power BI dashboards. Challenges encountered, such as data inaccuracies and limited connectivity, were mitigated through strategies allowing multiple uploads of the same data type for the targeted period. Lessons learned highlight the system's adaptability, ease of integration, and the need for precise data specifications. Looking ahead, recommendations include automating deployment processes, integrating with broader systems like ERP, and refining indicator definitions to support new use cases. These steps aim to ensure scalability, enhanced system capabilities, and seamless future deployments.

The AI services have the goal of leveraging the data available in the IQS to generate additional information, also generating new data if it was not previously available. These services range from material quality and size analysis, volume calculation, anomalies detection or production forecast, to natural language-based document retrieval. All these services have been updated and refined during the last part of the project, to deploy missing hardware, improve the algorithms or finalize the visualization dashboards. All services have succeeded in their goal of automating certain processes, increase knowledge or improve efficiency in the quarries. One of the main challenges has been the deployment of hardware in such harsh environments, which requires careful consideration to the protection of the components. Future deployments will consider using a real-time dashboard for time sensitive alarms and increasing the number of sensors to improve the modelling results.

Regarding the Data Warehouse, this component is in charge of storing business-related historical information. It retrieves data from the data lake and other external sources, aggregates it and stores it in a structured way. During this period, new tables have been created to be able to store newly generated data, such as weather information. Its integration with the remaining DEQ infrastructure has been successful, thanks to standard interfaces and data formats that facilitates the connection with other components. For the future, correct dimensioning of the storage solution must be a priority, and automating the pipeline deployment and update process would improve the availability and ease of maintenance of the system.

The BIM system created digital representations of quarry sites, connecting physical assets with operational data through a Common Data Environment (CDE).

Support activities included stakeholder coordination, system monitoring, and data integration optimization. A structured issue resolution framework addressed challenges like synchronization delays and model performance issues. Refinements were implemented across all pilot sites based on operational feedback—enhancing production visualization at Holcim, improving maintenance integration at Vicat, optimizing consumption and machinery data display at Cemex, enhancing equipment efficiency analysis at Cimpor, and refining topographic representation at CSI.

Key achievements include successful 3D model implementation for all sites, integration with various data types, and development of customized visualization tools. Challenges involved aligning technical possibilities with operational needs and managing varying data availability. Future deployment recommendations include standardized modelling protocols, phased implementation, and comprehensive training resources.

The BIM integration established a foundation for enhanced operational visibility, demonstrating the potential for digital transformation in the quarrying sector while complementing the broader DigiEcoQuarry ecosystem.

2 Introduction

2.1 Deliverable objectives

This report documents the continuous support provided to pilot sites and the subsequent refinements made to the deployed Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools. Task T4.6 focused on maintaining the functionality of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), ensuring seamless data flow between systems, and addressing any technical malfunctions encountered. Additionally, the task involved monitoring and resolving ICT-related issues reported by pilot sites during operations. Based on the feedback and data collected, necessary refinements were implemented to enhance the performance and user experience of the ICT tools. This report provides a comprehensive overview of the support activities, issues encountered, and the refinements made, aiming to guide future improvements and deployments.

2.2 Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is public.

2.3 Structure of the report

This report is structured as the following:

Executive Summary: This section provides a concise summary of the entire report, highlighting the main findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Introduction: The introduction sets the context for the report, detailing the deliverable objectives and the intended audience. It also includes this structure section to guide the reader through the report's organization.

Intelligent Quarrying System: This section delves into the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), covering continuous support activities, issue monitoring and resolution, refinements of ICT tools, and challenges and lessons learned. It concludes with recommendations for future improvements.

AI Services: This section describes the refinements, integration and deployment of various AI services at different sites, including quality determination, grain size determination, stockpile volume calculation, production and consumption forecasting, and anomalies detection. It also addresses challenges, lessons learned, and recommendations.

Data Warehouse: This section revisits the architecture of the data warehouse, discusses interfaces and tables, and highlights challenges and lessons learned, along with recommendations for future refinements.

Building Information Modelling: This section focuses on the Building Information Modelling application, discussing its components, challenges, lessons learned, and recommendations for future improvements.

Conclusions: The final section summarizes the achievements of the project and proposes actions for future deployments.

3 Intelligent Quarrying System

The DigiEcoQuarry project represents a significant milestone in the realm of quarrying operations, fostering a digital transformation of traditional practices, thereby optimizing production, transport, improving environmental performance, ensuring safety, and promoting sustainable practices. The project revolves around the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), which serves as the central platform integrating various digital technologies, expert systems, and data sources to streamline operations, enhance efficiency, and provide data-driven insights.

The IQS incorporates a range of components, including a data lake platform, Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure, expert systems, Business Information Modelling (BIM), Artificial Intelligence (AI) services, Data Warehouse, Power BI ecosystem, and Azure cloud services. These components served to build a data collection and storage infrastructure and a data management platform embracing a microservice architecture. Microservices break down the system into modular, manageable components, enhancing agility, scalability, and fault tolerance. This approach streamlines development, maintenance, and updates, allowing for the rapid adaptation of services to evolving quarrying requirements, processes, and operations.

Several quarry processes (Transport, Production, Automation, Environment, etc.) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format. Additionally, every interaction within our system occurs over secure HTTPS connections, providing a robust layer of security that safeguards pilot sites data and ensures the privacy of the users.

The data integration process has been implemented at the five pilot sites. Data are flowing at various frequencies (hourly, daily, monthly) depending on the use case. Data integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern adopted by all data providers to push data from expert systems to the IQS and to pull data from the IQS by the data consumers.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring.

The implementation of the IQS and site's specific development were described in D4.6 "Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment". More details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site, are described in section 3.1 of D4.6.
- The Centralized Data Management Platform and the CDMP front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.6.
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6.
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6.
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6.
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6.

The following sections will describe the monitoring and maintenance operations carried out to ensure the operational maintenance of the IQS. Additionally, the incident management process and conflict resolution methods will be detailed. Finally, all modifications and improvements made will be specifically documented for each pilot site, as well as globally for the platform and associated tools.

3.1 Continuous support activities

3.1.1 Stakeholders

The users involved include the pilot site, the expert system provider (KTA), AI services, and BIM. User management was handled through Active Directory and Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) and Keycloak system, ensuring secure access. Users were created upon request to provide access to IQS, and continuous support was provided to pilot site users and data providers for accessing and using IQS components. To accommodate the evolving expert systems of data providers, configurations for uploading tools were adapted accordingly. Additionally, access to GitHub projects was granted to share specific tools (proxies) with the pilot sites, facilitating collaboration and resource sharing.

3.1.2 Monitoring of the IQS components

The monitoring of IQS components includes several key activities. VM surveys are conducted to check the running status, free disk space, and OS updates. The manual operating mode set up during the implementation of IQS led to the definition of survey processes, which were then automated using Ansible as the core solution.

Additionally, IQS components are surveyed for their running status and logs are continuously watched. Automating these tasks allows the team to be reactive and often anticipate issues raised by users in case of system failure, which is crucial for providing a system with minimal downtime.

Furthermore, a Microsoft Azure cloud solution has been set up to make continuous backups of VMs and databases, maintaining a history of seven days.

3.1.3 Maintenance of the IQS components

During this period, quarries and quarry partners data providers refined their data and made new data available, which rendered already uploaded data obsolete or inaccurate. Consequently, some datasets had to be cleaned and replaced by new uploads of the same data type for the targeted period. These new uploads automatically triggered data processing, thereby updating databases and KPIs. Subsequently, the dashboards were updated using the corrected data.

To facilitate data renewal, new scripts for data cleaning and upload by period were created. These scripts utilize the IQS API developed for CDMP and IQS services. This operating mode proved to be relevant because the data providing systems or data quality were not always reliable, often due to failing sensors.

3.1.4 Data integration

New proxy data connectors were developed to ingest data from pilot sites when providing new access to their data sources. These proxies were uploaded to a GitHub project and shared with the concerned partners. Additionally, a new service for DHP uploads was configured and deployed so that DHP could provide data for CSI pilot site. Similarly, a new service for Arco uploads was developed and configured so that Arco could provide data for Vicat and Cimpor pilot sites.

3.2 Issue monitoring and resolution

3.2.1 Process for reporting issues

The process for reporting issues begins when an issue is sent to the deq-iqs-support team at deq-iqs-support@akkodis.com. Alternatively, an issue can be raised during the T4.6 monthly call. Once an issue is reported, a change request is created. This change request is then analysed, planned, corrected, tested, and finally deployed.

3.2.2 Common issues encountered

Several common issues were encountered during the operation of IQS. One significant issue involved the Microsoft Azure cloud provider, where some VMs failed to start, including both PS VMs and the Keycloak VM. This failure made it impossible to connect to IQS and upload data. By collaborating with Azure support experts, these issues were resolved.

IQS security rules and procedures were continuously updated and applied, following recommendations from IT and security teams, as well as those from the cloud provider. Additionally, some IQS services faced issues with cleaning temporary upload files, which led to a file system full error.

To ensure communication security, script hooks were created for the automatic rebuild of keystores hosting SSL certificates, which are automatically renewed by the encryption service. Furthermore, some quarries or data providers had unusual working hours, leading to data upload failures as IQS VMs were powered off during the night and weekends to save costs and reduce environmental impact. This problem was resolved by simply tuning the running hours of some VMs.

3.2.3 Resolution strategies

The resolution strategy depends on the type and criticality of the problem. For blocking bugs, immediate consideration, correction, testing, and deployment are required, as outlined in D4.5 Test & Deployment. For non-blocking bugs, the tasks are planned, corrected, tested, and then deployed. In the case of evolutions, the process involves assessment, planning before development phase.

All corrections and evolutions are performed and validated following the procedures defined in D4.2 Report on IQS design, specifically in chapter 5, IQS Test Plan, paragraph 5.3 Methodology and Process Applied.

3.3 Refinements of ICT Tools

3.3.1 Identification of Refinement Needs

After analysing all the modifications and improvements made from the integration phase to the validation phase of the IQS, the following table summarizes the key aspects of refinement in ICT tools that must be considered in future work:

Table 1. Key aspects of refinement in ICT tools.

Aspect	Description
Technical Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fixing software bugs or hardware glitches. - Improving performance metrics like speed, reliability, and efficiency. - Enhancing compatibility and interoperability.
Usability Improvements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Refining the user interface (UI) for better intuitiveness and accessibility. - Simplifying workflows for user efficiency. - Incorporating accessibility standards.
Feature Optimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding, modifying, or removing features based on relevance and effectiveness. - Streamlining features to align with user priorities and reduce redundancy.
Data integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding new data source, new reference data and configuration table. - Data cleaning, Data modification.
Scalability and Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensuring the tools scale to meet varying demands or integrate into larger systems. - Adapting the tools to different operational environments.
Security and Privacy Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Addressing vulnerabilities identified during testing. - Strengthening data protection measures to comply with regulations and user expectations.

Aspect	Description
Feedback Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysing user and stakeholder feedback to identify pain points. - Iteratively implementing changes and re-evaluating performance post-refinement.

3.3.2 Holcim

In the context of Holcim PS, due to data accuracy and validation issues, various tools were developed to clean the system and restart the upload process. Consequently, the entire system needs to be ready to accept multiple uploads of the same data. Indeed, data providers can decide at any moment to re-upload data from the SCADA system due to the deployment of corrective actions for various reasons.

Using the system 5 days a week during working hours has proven to be a good option to significantly reduce costs. The concept of a data proxy appears to be relevant and adequate. Several versions were created (in Python and .Net) for exchanging production and SCADA data.

3.3.3 Vicat

In the context of Vicat, the activities focused on finalizing the services that collect, store, and process mobile crusher data generated by the Metso system, as well as H&S data and their respective dashboards. Regarding the integration with the Vicat SCADA system, the data were collected by Maestro and made available in the data lake. However, due to the delay in the deployment of the production chain, we have not been able to test the system as it is still in the validation phase.

3.3.4 Cemex

In the context of CEMEX, since it was not possible to connect to the production system, we developed a connector to retrieve production data in Excel format and populate the data lake with correctly formatted data. This data enabled the creation of dashboards tailored to CEMEX.

Additionally, we integrated with the Sandvik system (Drilling System). This integration allowed us to create a new connector for UPM-M that enables the integration of the Matlab environment with the data lake.

3.3.5 Cimpor

In the context of Cimpor, we completed the integration with the Arco system by developing a new connector that connects to the Arco SCADA system, retrieves, and stores production data. This data serves to adapt the plant production dashboard. We also completed the implementation of a new service dedicated to ITK that collects H&S data to feed a new dashboard with H&S data. Additionally, with SIGMA, we accomplished the integration of a dashboard developed by Sigma into the existing application.

3.3.6 CSI

In the context of CSI, we developed a dashboard to monitor mobile machinery costs. By integrating machinery costs, including the cost of fuel (updated monthly), the cost of idling (OEM and monthly updated cost), and the cost of working (OEM and monthly updated cost) into the IQS, we managed to combine the DHP indicator with machinery costs. This integration allowed us to create a new family of machinery cost indicators.

3.3.7 IQS platform refinement

At the IQS level, refinement activities can be summarized as follows:

The Azure Data Lake was configured with data spaces and containers. Virtual machines underwent cost optimization, security management, and backup and restore processes. Azure Power BI Services saw optimization in the configuration and deployment pipelines, as well as in Power BI applications.

The central data management platform experienced improvements in the configuration and deployment of the applications (back-end, front-end), raw data processing and management, and the addition of raw data processing for

mobile machinery. Latency was optimized, and integration with the time series database was achieved. IQS services were further optimized for better integration. Talend processes were standardized, and the launching of processing pipelines was optimized.

The GitHub environment was enhanced to improve code sharing with partners.

Finally, Let's Encrypt certificates and secure keys management were harmonized across all services, including the CDMP frontend and backend, microservices, databases, Keycloak server, and InfluxDB server.

3.4 Challenges and Lessons Learned

3.4.1 Insights from Operational Feedback

The IQS architecture, based on Spring-boot Java framework, proved to be highly relevant due to its modularity, which allows for the simple integration of new services and their independent deployment and startup. Keycloak was an efficient solution for managing authentication and authorizations to access IQS components and secure inter-service communication. The data lake provided unlimited data storage, managed by one of the main cloud providers.

Using Talend as an ETL tool eased the complex processing of raw data for KPI generation. Proxy applications were very relevant as versatile upload interfaces between any system and data type and IQS. Power BI was found to be simple for defining applications and allowed for the continuous update of dashboards.

The successful integration of real-time data from dust sensors demonstrated that IQS is capable of integrating with any IoT device.

However, not all expected indicators could be calculated by IQS due to the unavailability of some data (such as REE, water and energy consumption, and sales). Nevertheless, models were defined and integrated, and were tested using simulated data. By taking advantage of the versatility of proxies, IQS could be fed with data even in the case of non-connected quarries by using Excel files as a data source.

The experience of the project allowed us to define the specifications of all the necessary data and their sources. The next step would be to read this data at its source using specific connectors (proxies) while respecting the constraints of availability, security, and confidentiality of this data.

3.4.2 Recommendations for Future Refinements

Effective processing of raw data, particularly through time series data processing, requires a different type of architecture based on TICK Stack ¹ components. This architecture will be developed. Apart from SCADA systems, no interface with the quarry expert systems has been set up. Now that IQS is mature and secure, it could be interfaced with ERP, SAP, and other systems without risks.

The task of defining indicators has been very time-consuming, and we were unable to collect all the expected indicators, such as REE. The calculation of some indicators was complicated because it required data from systems such as maintenance, planning, sales, and consumables, which were not directly connectable to the IQS at that time. The integration of these systems will simplify the calculation of new indicators.

Therefore, it appears that the definition of indicators is a key task to achieve project goals, and it should be managed with high priority and particular care.

¹TICK stands for Telegraf, InfluxDB, Chronograf, and Kapacitor, which are integrated in a cohesive architecture, or "stack". <https://www.influxdata.com/time-series-platform/>

4 AI Services

This section focuses on improvements and support activities carried out for the different AI Services during the last period of the project.

4.1 Continuous support activities

4.1.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders for the AI services developed in DEQ are quarry operators and management personnel, depending on the particular service. Access to all services is provided through Power BI dashboards, which provide their own authentication system. Service accounts have been created to access necessary data when needed. The exception is the MetaQuarry service, for which an ad-hoc user interface has been developed. This UI has its own user management system, having created users for the partners involved (Holcim and Vicat).

4.1.2 Monitoring of the AI Services

Due to the difference amongst services, the strategies to monitor them range from periodic manual checks to ensure that the service is online, to automatic monitoring via Zabbix to be notified of issues in the virtual machines where the services are deployed.

Other aspect of the services that needs to be monitored is the sending of data from sensors or captured devices. This monitoring is done through the platform that handles the LoRa network (The Things Network), with periodic checks, or ensuring that the files are up to date in case the data reaches Sigma's offices directly.

Mobile connectivity and data consumption is also kept track of through the KITE platform, a Telefonica managed tool for IoT mobile connectivity.

Lastly, the PCs deployed in the quarries can be accessed directly through a VPN configured for that purpose.

4.1.3 Maintenance of the AI Services

During this period, several maintenance activities have taken place, mainly focused on sensors and cameras deployed on the field. For the sensors, a visit to the Alenquer quarry has been necessary in a couple of occasions when some of the sensors stopped sending data.

For the cameras, the image quality has been continuously monitored and the camera parameters adjusted to improve the quality as much as possible. Besides, due to the harsh environment they are deployed in, it has been necessary to clean the lenses when they became too dusty. A restart of the PCs that manage the cameras has also been required twice since they have been deployed. Both of these tasks have been performed by quarry personnel.

4.1.4 Data integration

Data generated by the services is uploaded to the Data Warehouse as it is generated. This is done through data pipelines that have been described in deliverable D4.4. During this period, new pipelines have been created as new data has been available.

4.2 Issue monitoring and resolution

4.2.1 Process for reporting issues

The Sigma – UPM team has kept close contact with quarry owners and other stakeholders involved in the services. Whenever an issue has arisen, they have had direct contact with Sigma and UPM employees to notify them of the issue. The monthly T4.6 calls have been another way to raise potential problems.

4.2.2 Common issues encountered

Different issues have occurred during this period. The dust sensors deployed in Alenquer have stopped sending data in some occasions, mostly due to running out of battery, although a software bug was also identified and fixed.

As reported in the previous section, camera lenses have also needed cleaning, although image quality has never become an important issue.

4.2.3 Resolution strategies

Issues have been promptly resolved due to the close cooperation between Sigma, UPM and the quarry operators, who have always been available and willing to facilitate any maintenance or repairing task. The monitoring in place via Zabbix allows to detect these issues in a timely fashion.

Software issues have been resolved internally between the R&D and IT teams in Sigma. The issue management tool that is in place in the company allows to properly prioritize and tackle these issues.

Furthermore, systems are restarted daily when possible (the CEMEX monitoring system, for instance), to ensure that they are available if quarry personnel are not present for a manual restart or if a network failure made remote connection impossible.

4.3 Refinements of AI Services

4.3.1 Identification of Refinement Needs

During the last period of the project, several refinements had to be implemented to the AI services. These refinements and support activities are summarized in the following table:

Table 2. Refinement needs for AI services.

Service	Pilot Site	Description
Quality determination	CEMEX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality models: data collection, model training, evaluation, deployment, monitoring and iterative refinement. Fixing software bugs or hardware issues. Refinement of Power BI dashboards.
Grain size determination	CEMEX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grain size model: data collection, model training, evaluation, deployment, monitoring and iterative refinement. Fixing software bugs or hardware issues. Refinement of Power BI dashboards.
Stockpile volume calculation	HOLCIM, VICAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of mobile application.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and deployment of processing pipeline.
Anomaly detection	CSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-site data gathering. • Development and deployment of audio models.
Production and consumption forecast	CIMPOR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of water counters and wind sensors. • Development and refinement of forecast models. • Refinement of Power BI dashboards.
MetaQuarry	HOLCIM, VICAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated model. • Included integration with Google Drive.

In the following sections, more details will be provided for each of them.

4.3.2 Holcim

This section describes the updates to the services deployed in Holcim: the stockpile volume calculation service and MetaQuarry.

4.3.2.1 Stockpile volume calculation service

For a more detailed information of the latest developments, can be added D6.9 “Pilot (IT) Technical report and achieved results (2|2)”

4.3.2.1.1 Service Integration and deployment

The app versions were completed simplifying the user experience considerably, moreover the backend infrastructure, and processing pipeline (models) were tested and validated. The solution validation was completed by using on geo-referenced video outputs on a single app using videos recorded at HOLCIM and VICAT, as well as others taken in other quarry sites, including CEMEX Valdilecha, during a visit. The video footage collected, and the results obtained were validated by all teams involved. The level of precision was found to be sufficient, as well as the details offered. From then on, activities focused on building a fully operative prototype of the service, integrating the whole APP experience and required backend.

Figure 1. Different shots of the APP interface to record the stockpiles videos.

4.3.2.1.2 Models

The reconstruction models were updated and introduced additional ones to expedite the volume computation process, 3D model reconstruction, and pixel matching. As a result, the entire processing pipeline has been updated to incorporate all these new capabilities. We run systematic tests to validate the system's performance.

4.3.2.2 Video data masking

We introduced several refinements to the pixel filtering process to expedite the reconstruction, using state-of-the-art segmentation models to produce masks on the video data. In doing this, the pixel-matching algorithms can focus on the pile and ignore the surroundings, especially the sky. An example is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Segmentation of random frames on a given sequence. In orange the segmented parts, in this case, the sky.

The resulting masks are used in the pixel matching by focusing on the areas corresponding to the stockpiles. This pre-processing expedites the matching process, the parameters of which have also been tuned. As a result, a 31% decrease in processing time was achieved.

4.3.2.3 Full processing pipeline

For estimating material stockpile volumes (or other objects), a modular pipeline was followed consisting of three main stages:

1. *Preprocessing*: From a video capturing the stockpile (ideally encircling it completely), we execute:
 - a. Frame extraction: Decompose video into frames containing (or later enriched with) metadata about the capture device's position, orientation, and timestamp.
 - b. Intelligent frame selection: Optimize computational efficiency by selecting only frames with significant visual variance, as consecutive frames often provide redundant information.
 - c. Masking: Remove irrelevant regions from frames that don't contribute to reconstruction.
 - d. Flare and glare removal: Mitigate sun glare artefacts that significantly distort mound reconstruction accuracy.
 - e. Metadata handling: Add external metadata to frames if not embedded during capture.
2. *Reconstruction*: Uses SfM algorithms:
 - a. Input: Pre-processed frames with the highest reconstruction relevance.
 - b. Output: Noisy 3D point cloud of the reconstructed stockpile/object.
3. *Postprocessing*
 - a. Filtering: To remove outliers. Signal processing techniques achieve significant noise reduction.
 - b. Meshing: Convert filtered point cloud into a triangular mesh with vertices at reconstructed points.
 - c. Volume estimation: Calculate stockpile volume using the tetrahedron method from triangular mesh.

Several stages of this pipeline require GPU acceleration on the AI models. These include intelligent frame selection, masking, flare and glare removal, and output denoising.

The entire processing pipeline for the video footage is illustrated in Figure 3. The referred metadata includes georeferencing, relative orientation, and position information to ease 3D reconstruction.

The video input is the first step, then the process the video sequences is started, then geolocation and other metadata are incorporated. The following stages match the previous description of the pipeline.

Figure 3. The complete processing pipeline for volume estimation.

The mesh obtained, along with the coloured generated image for a pile, is illustrated in Figure 4. We focus on the underlying mesh structure for volume computation. The final pipeline can compute volume with less than 1% error, provided that a reference measure is available (i.e., at the least the georeferenced information).

Figure 4. Snapshot on the complete 3D reconstruction of a pile.

4.3.2.3.1 Service outputs

At the end of all the video and modelling processes the recorded piles are reconstructed as shown in the last figure.

4.3.2.3.1.1 Data visualization APP

The current version of the user APP incorporates visualisation capabilities for the results of the stockpile volume computation. Tests with final users are still pending.

4.3.2.3.1.2 Stockpile volume dashboard

The design of the stockpile volume dashboard for Power BI was completed, following the recommendations of the sites and other services.

4.3.2.4 MetaQuarry

4.3.2.4.1 Service integration and Deployment

As it has already been introduced in past deliverables, MetaQuarry aims at providing a convenient way to find and retrieve digital documents through the usage of natural language. It integrates with existing repositories and is capable of answering user questions with the information contained in the repository documents.

The architecture of the service has already been described in D4.6 and updated in D6.7 and D6.9. It has not suffered important changes since it was reported. It is reproduced below for convenience:

Figure 5. MetaQuarry's architecture

The service is conceived to require no additional hardware from the quarry. It is deployed at Sigma's premises, in high-availability infrastructure, and can be accessed from any terminal with an internet connection.

4.3.2.4.2 Models

The model MetaQuarry is based on has also remained largely unchanged since it was reported in D4.6. It uses Mixtral, an LLM developed by mistral.ai. An in-depth description can be found in the mentioned deliverable, along with D6.9.

It is worth mentioning the addition of a new functionality: the possibility of accessing documents located in Google Drive. This was motivated by conversations with Holcim representatives, who explained how they store most documents in this system. Thus, to avoid having to move all quarry documents to a new system in order to use MetaQuarry, it was decided to integrate Google Drive as a compatible repository.

With this latest inclusion, MetaQuarry is finally compatible with four storage alternatives:

- DEQ's data lake.
- Private cloud.
- MS Teams.
- Google Drive.

4.3.2.4.3 Service outputs

All interactions with this service are carried out through MetaQuarry's interface. This interface is a web portal, accessible online, that provides access to all functionalities of the service. The image below shows a capture of this web interface:

Figure 6. MetaQuarry's interface.

From this interface, a user can generate questions about the documentation included in the service, test a series of sample questions, revise the uploaded documents or configure the document repositories.

A more in-depth description of this interface has been included in deliverables D6.7 and D6.9.

4.3.3 Vicat

This section describes the updates carried out on the services deployed in Vicat: the stockpile volume calculation service and MetaQuarry.

4.3.3.1 Stockpile volume calculation

For this service please refer to section 4.3.2.1, since the service considered is identical.

4.3.3.2 MetaQuarry

The updates to the service described in the previous HOLCIM section, also apply to Vicat's implementation of MetaQuarry. Please refer to it.

4.3.4 Cemex

This section describes the updates carried out on the two services deployed in Cemex: the quality and granulometry services.

4.3.4.1 Quality determination service

4.3.4.1.1 Hardware Integration, Deployment and Monitoring

The quality determination service has the goal of analysing the quality of the material that enters the plant. It uses cameras to monitor the main crusher and the C3 conveyor belt, applying computer vision algorithms to determine the amount of clay in the material as well as the size of the fragments that reach the crusher and its occupation.

The hardware deployed in Valdilecha quarry for this service has been thoroughly described in deliverables D4.3 and D4.6. As a quick summary, two cameras have been installed, pointing at the crusher mouth and the C3 conveyor belt, along with a lightning array for the belt and a computer to receive and send images.

Figure 7. Hardware deployed at Valdilecha for quality determination service: crusher camera (left), C3 conveyor belt camera (middle) and computer (right).

During this period, both cameras and PC have been stable, capturing and sending images daily. Punctual issues, such as not receiving images for some hours, have been quickly solved thanks to the cooperation of the quarry personnel, who just had to restart the service computer.

Maintenance has been limited to the monitoring of the camera parameters, such as exposure or capture rate, to make them optimal to most light conditions; and the cleaning of the camera lenses. Cleaning has only been necessary on two occasions, which, given the dusty conditions of the quarry, is a surprisingly low number of times. The images below show the difference of the captured images before and after cleaning the camera lens:

Figure 8. Image of the crusher before (left) and after (right) cleaning the camera lens

4.3.4.1.2 Models

This section is focused on describing the updates to the computer vision models that are in charge of processing the images captured by the cameras installed in the quarry and generating the different outputs which are ultimately presented to the final user. As an overview, the Quality determination service is composed of two components: DEQ01-C3, focused on analysing material sizes and colorimetry in the C3 belt; and DEQ01-Crusher, focused on analysing material sizes and occupation in the crusher. Both components have an associated camera, whose images are gathered by a PC located in the quarry, as shown in following figure:

Figure 9. Quality determination service summary.

The starting point for this section is the development of the models described in deliverable D4.3. During their evaluation, it was found that different refinements were required, for which a series of activities took place. These activities (data collection, model training, evaluation, deployment, monitoring and iterative refinement) were carried out since November 2023 and are described in deliverable D6.8.

4.3.4.1.2.1 Crusher

As mentioned before, the crusher algorithms have the goal of analysing the occupation and size of rock fragments found in the primary crusher, through computer vision-based image segmentation. This task involves segmenting the image into two categories: background and foreground.

In this context, Sigma established a computer vision system to analyse the crusher, which can help the quarry:

- **Increase crusher performance** analysing the material flow enables the evaluation of the crusher’s efficiency by measuring output consistency, throughput rates, and particle size distribution. This information can identify potential bottlenecks, optimize crusher settings, and detect equipment wear or malfunction even if it does not observe the crushing process itself. Instead, it analyses the waste-collecting belt placed just under the crusher.

To develop this system, several steps were needed:

1. **Dataset generation:** image data description and data generation pipeline.

2. **Segmentation model:** exploration of the segmentation model used for the image analysis. The chosen approach acknowledges the need for hand-made annotations to achieve to achieve high-quality image segmentation with minimal human annotations. More details about this process can be found in Annex 9.1.
3. **Information sharing:** pipeline for info sharing with the quarrying company.

These steps are represented in the pipeline show in the following figure:

Figure 10. Automatic pipeline for the image analysis and post-processing at the DEQ01-Crusher.

The result of this process is a segmented image without background, as shown below:

Figure 11. Result of the crusher pipeline: original image (left), initial segmentation mask (middle), and final annotated image after human refinement (right).

More details about this process can be found in Annex 0.

4.3.4.1.2.2 C3 conveyor belt

The C3 conveyor belt algorithms have the goal of determining the quality of the input material in the quarry in terms of clay and limestone contents.

This belt carries material discarded from the crushing process, typically fine particles, dust, and irregular fragments of rock that do not meet the required specifications for commercial use. The analysis of such material can be used for studying the performance of the crusher as well as for analysing the fraction of good material that is discarded through the conveyor belt.

In this context, Sigma established a computer vision system to analyse the C3 conveyor belt, which can bring several advantages to the quarry:

- **Stock distribution analytics:** Monitoring the material on the C3 conveyor provides insights into the distribution of different aggregate sizes and their proportions, allowing for better stockpile management. This helps optimize inventory tracking, reduce material imbalances, and ensure a consistent supply of desired products.
- **Input material quality:** Assessing the material on the conveyor allows quality control of the raw feed. This includes tracking particle composition, identifying contamination, and evaluating moisture content through colorimetry. The monitoring ensures that the input meets processing standards and supports adjustments to maintain product quality.
- **Recirculation evaluation:** By looking at the waste collecting belt, the material entering the recirculation pipeline can be analysed, and the correlation between raw input, primary production and secondary production can be established through recirculation.

To develop this system, several steps were needed:

1. **Dataset generation:** image data description and data generation pipeline.
2. **Segmentation and Classification model:** exploration of the segmentation and classification model used for the image analysis.
3. **Colorimetry analysis:** usage of the segmentation and classification data to produce the colorimetry of the limestone and clay materials in each image.

4. **Information sharing:** pipeline for info sharing with the quarrying company.

These steps are represented in the pipeline show in the following figure:

Figure 12. Automatic pipeline for the image analysis and post-processing at the DEQ01-C3 conveyor belt.

The process starts with the capture of belt images through one of the cameras deployed in the quarry to create a high-quality training dataset for the algorithm. These images are then segmented, following a process similar to the one used for the granulometry service described in the next section.

After this, masks for limestone and clay pixels are obtained. With this pixel-level information, the colorimetry process matches each sample against a standardized Munsell colour.

Once the granulometry and colorimetry is done for every picture captured with the camera, a JSON file is generated containing the information relative to the timestamp, the granulometry and also the number of instances at each sieve size with respect the area, shortest side and longest side of each segmented stone. This information is automatically uploaded to the Data Warehouse to be visualized from a Power BI dashboard, described in the next section.

More information about this process can be found in Annex O.

4.3.4.1.3 Service outputs

The outputs of this service are stored in the Data Warehouse and visualized from Power BI. Different dashboards have been created for this task, following the DigiEcoQuarry look and feel, and are detailed below.

4.3.4.1.3.1 Crusher

This dashboard shows the result of the analysis performed by the crusher algorithms:

Figure 13. Quality determination service dashboard (crusher).

It displays several pieces of information. In first place, the blue line (and its corresponding data points) shows the occupation percentage of the crusher at a given point. The handle below allows to filter for a specific day of time frame.

Secondly, the dotted light blue line represents the threshold above which the occupation level might start to pose a problem for the crusher.

Lastly, the colour of the occupation level gives an indication of whether a too big rock fragment has been detected, which is represented by the red numbers.

4.3.4.1.3.2 C3 conveyor belt

This dashboard shows the result of the C3 conveyor algorithms:

Figure 14. Quality determination service dashboard (C3 belt).

The first graph on the top part represents the amount of clay (reddish colour) and limestone (brownish colour) in the C3 belt at a given moment. This graph can be filtered to focus on a specific instant with the filter handle found on the bottom of the dashboard.

The bottom-left part of the dashboard provides an indication of the actual colour of the clay and limestone in the belt. It also provides the Munsell code of said colour. The timestamp on top of the colour boxes corresponds to the last update of the data.

Lastly, in the bottom-right part, a weather report for the current day, as reported by AEMET, can be found. A link to a weather history for the past days is also provided.

4.3.4.1.3.3 Events

For both the quality determination and the granulometry services (described in the next section) an additional dashboard has been created, to gather abnormal events that have been detected during the processing:

Date	Service	Description	Priority
16/01/2024 9:30:00	Quality	Oversize	High
16/01/2024 11:15:00	Grain Size	>40	High

Figure 15. Events dashboard for quality and granulometry services.

These events are the detection of an oversize fragments that could block the crusher for the quality determination service, and the detection of anomalous size distributions in the case of the granulometry service.

4.3.4.2 Grain size determination service

4.3.4.2.1 Hardware Integration, Deployment and Monitoring

The grain size determination service has the goal of analysing the size distribution of rock fragments in a final product's conveyor belt, in this case the C33 belt, which corresponds to the 4/20 product.

As before, the hardware used in this service has been described in deliverables D4.3 and D4.6, although a short summary is shown below:

Figure 16. Hardware for granulometry service: camera and lights (left), antenna (centre) and computer (right).

The service makes use of a camera and lightning system to capture belt images, a computer to gather and send these images and an antenna, to enable 4G communications for the computer.

During this last period of the project, the system has been stable, gathering images daily. Punctual issues have been promptly resolved by the quarry personnel with a restart.

4.3.4.2.2 Models

As explained in section 4.3.4.1.2, the starting point for this section is the development of the models described in deliverable D4.3. During their evaluation, it was found that different refinements were required, for which a series of activities took place. These activities (data collection, model training, evaluation, deployment, monitoring and iterative refinement) were carried out since November 2023 and are also described in deliverable D6.8.

The granulometry service aims at providing an estimation of the size distribution of a certain product. Traditionally, these granulometric curves are generated with a manual procedure consisting on extracting few kilograms of material for the later determination of particles sizes through sieving. Thus, the service attempts to obtain this information through computer vision methods, reducing the human labour involved and the downtime for the quarry.

In order to develop this system, several steps were needed:

- **Dataset generation:** image data description and data generation pipeline.
- **Segmentation model:** exploration of the segmentation model used for the image analysis.
- **Granulometry generation:** usage of the segmentation data to produce the granulometry.
- **Information sharing:** pipeline for info sharing with the quarrying company.

Each of these steps are represented in the following figure:

Figure 17. Pipeline for granulometry service.

The result of this process is a segmented image in which each segment's size is estimated, as shown in the following image:

Figure 18. Example of granulometry generation.

Once the granulometry is done for every picture, a JSON file is generated containing the information relative to the timestamp, the granulometry and also the number of instances at each sieve size with respect the area, shortest side and longest side of each segmented stone. This information is stored in the Data Warehouse to be visualized in a Power BI dashboard. More information about this process can be found in Annex 0.

4.3.4.2.3 Service outputs

This dashboard shows the output of the granulometry service:

Figure 19. Granulometry service dashboard.

There are two graphs in this dashboard: the top one shows the size distribution of the material, measured in percentage of fragments in each size range, while the bottom one shows this information as a total number of fragments in each size range. In both cases, the shortest side, longest side and area strategies are displayed simultaneously.

The filter handle on the bottom of the dashboard allows to filter the graphs temporarily, to focus on a certain time period.

4.3.5 Cimpor

This section describes the updates carried out on the Forecast service deployed in Cimpor’s quarry.

4.3.5.1 Production and consumption forecast service

4.3.5.1.1 Hardware Integration and deployment

As it was described in D4.3, this service uses a combination of data from sensors, open sources and quarry information to:

1. Minimize the amount of water used to mitigate the dust generated in the quarry.
2. Optimize the production rate considering the meteorological conditions and the past production history.
3. Estimate the periods when the plant can operate using a high percentage of clean energy.

This section will focus on the sensors that have been deployed in CIMPOR’s quarry in Alenquer, which are:

- 4 dust sensors.
- 1 wind sensor.

- 2 water counters.

The sensors communicate over LoRa, sending their data to a gateway which, in turn, sends these data to a network server and, from there, to the IQS. The following figure shows the updated architecture of the hardware components:

Figure 20. Forecast service's hardware architecture.

All sensors have been deployed in the quarry according to the following map:

Figure 21. Location of the sensors in Alenquer quarry.

The main updates to each of these sensors are detailed below.

4.3.5.1.1.1 Dust sensors

As reported in D4.3 and D4.6, four different dust sensors are installed in the quarry, an industrial one and three custom-made. Since their deployment, they were under observation for several months, during which some of the custom-made sensors stopped sending data. They were revised and fixed during a visit to Alenquer to install the water sensors (described below), but started to show the same problems shortly after. They were then sent back to Sigma's office, where an issue in the firmware that caused a blocking condition was identified and fixed, as well as a problem in the wiring. After a period of observation where all sensors worked properly, they were sent back to the quarry, not having shown any other issue ever since.

Figure 22. LoRa Gateway (left) and dust sensor (right) deployed in Alenquer.

4.3.5.1.1.2 Water consumption sensors

As D4.6 introduced, two pulse counters were installed on corresponding water flow sensors, located in the quarry's water input lines, to make the water consumption readings available in the IQS. The images below show some pictures of the installation:

Figure 23. Water sensor and pulse counter (left), installation works (middle) and final installation of pulse counter (right).

Since their installation, the pulse counters have been sending data to the IQS, as the following figure shows:

Figure 24. Water consumption graph.

4.3.5.1.1.3 Wind sensor

Also introduced in D4.6, a wind sensor was planned to be installed, to have localized wind readings. The sensor was finally received (shown in Figure 25) and sent to the quarry, where it was installed by CIMPOR personnel.

Figure 25. Wind sensor (left) and controller box (right).

As the rest of the sensors, the anemometer has been sending wind direction and speed readings since its installation:

Figure 26. Wind sensor readings.

4.3.5.1.2 Models

This section describes the models that have been implemented in the Forecast service, as well as the previous analysis carried out on the available data.

The service is designed as an event-based architecture, which is scalable, fault tolerant and easy to maintain. It is shown in the following figure:

Figure 27. Forecast service's architecture.

The blocks on the left-hand side are in charge of retrieving data and storing it in the Data Warehouse. Whenever new data are available, an event is created. These events are consumed by the models, represented by the right-hand side blocks, which produce a result and generate an event themselves. These results are ultimately stored in the Data Warehouse.

The block in the middle, the Event Storage, gathers all events and distributes them amongst the different processes.

More details about each model are provided in the corresponding section below.

4.3.5.1.2.1 Water consumption

This section describes the Water Consumption Analysis model, which corresponds to the following block of the architecture:

Figure 28. Water Consumption Analysis model.

The water consumption service is based on a linear regression model. The previous work that has been carried out to reach this conclusion can be found in Annex 0. This model predicts the consumption by the end of the year, as well as the date in which the consumption limit would be reached.

It uses as input the following information:

date	timestamp	pulse
2025-01-03 09:10:05.642577 U...	1735895405	0.0
2025-01-03 09:25:05.613437 U...	1735896305	0.0
2025-01-03 09:40:05.609039 U...	1735897205	0.0
2025-01-03 09:55:05.634916 U...	1735898105	1.40000000000000...
2025-01-03 10:10:05.599359 U...	1735899005	2.80000000000000...
2025-01-03 10:25:05.604253 U...	1735899905	4.4
2025-01-03 10:40:05.569612 U...	1735900805	5.80000000000000...
2025-01-03 10:55:05.553060 U...	1735901705	7.4

Figure 29. Input data for water analysis model.

Date represents the date of the water measurement, *timestamp* is a conversion of the date in seconds, and *pulse* corresponds to the actual water measurements of the current year, from the beginning of the year and converted from pulses to litres.

With these data, it generates the following output:

date	consumption_limit	deadline	consumption	slope
2024-11-11 18:08:02.758695 U...	10000.0	2025-11-18 19:01:02.709687 U...	4607.882608217...	0.000193941086...
2024-11-11 18:08:04.006037 U...	10000.0	2025-11-24 15:16:41.836001 U...	4563.465433970...	0.000192050749...

Figure 30. Output of the water analysis model.

The variables are as follows:

- *Date*: date in which the prediction is carried out.
- *Consumption limit*: maximum allowed consumption for the quarry.
- *Deadline*: date in which it is expected to reach the consumption limit.
- *Consumption*: expected consumption by the end of the year at the current consumption pace.
- *Slope*: slope of the regression line. It equals the water consumption pace.

The model is run once per day. It retrieves the latest water consumption data for the current year, which is used to train the regression model. When the model is trained, a new output is generated and stored in the Data Warehouse

4.3.5.1.2.2 Clean energy prediction

This section describes the Electricity Consumption Analysis model, which corresponds to the following block of the architecture:

Figure 31. Electricity Consumption Analysis model.

The model is based on the previous work described in Annex O. It is conceived as two separate processes: the training of the model and generation of price predictions. This strategy allows to train the model automatically, without the need of stopping the service. The prediction process uses the most up-to-date model whenever it is run.

- **Model training**: this process is run once per day, being updated with the new data acquired that day. It uses the fitting function $Fit(w)$ described in the previous section. It uses as input the weather observations (wind speed) and the electricity prices in Portugal reported by OMIE. The following figure shows an extract of these input data:

date	month	day_of_week	quarter	hour	wind_speed	price
2025-02-24 00:00:00 UTC	2	2	1	0	1.4	79.21
2025-02-23 23:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	23	3.6	79.7
2025-02-23 22:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	22	1.8	100.9
2025-02-23 21:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	21	4.7	123.25
2025-02-23 20:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	20	3.2	134.7
2025-02-23 19:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	19	4.3	122.94
2025-02-23 18:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	18	7.6	100.9
2025-02-23 17:00:00 UTC	2	1	1	17	13.7	50.0

Figure 32. Input data for electricity analysis' training model.

The output of this process is a trained model that will be used by the price prediction process. It takes into account data from the past natural year, which helps the model evolve and not consider data that might be obsolete.

- **Price predictions**: this process is run hourly, which coincides with the frequency with which weather predictions are updated. It uses as input the previously-described trained model and weather predictions reported by OMIE:

date	month	day_of_week	quarter	hour	wind_speed
2025-03-04 02:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	2	6.5
2025-03-04 03:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	3	8.3
2025-03-04 04:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	4	7.2
2025-03-04 05:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	5	6.1
2025-03-04 06:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	6	5.8
2025-03-04 07:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	7	6.1
2025-03-04 08:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	8	8.3
2025-03-04 09:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	9	9.0
2025-03-04 10:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	10	9.0
2025-03-04 11:00:00 UTC	3	3	1	11	6.5

Figure 33. Input data for electricity analysis' prediction model

- The process outputs a price prediction for each hour (only working hours are considered). The full output has three fields: the date and time for when the prediction is generated, the update time and the predicted price itself. An example of this output is shown in following figure:

date	updated	price
2025-03-04 08:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	63.6300000...
2025-03-04 09:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	63.5440000...
2025-03-04 10:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	32.862
2025-03-04 11:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	39.124
2025-03-04 12:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	5.6
2025-03-04 13:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	29.714
2025-03-04 14:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	9.554
2025-03-04 15:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	58.798
2025-03-04 16:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	53.788
2025-03-04 17:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	47.142
2025-03-04 18:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	80.994
2025-03-04 19:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	103.520000...
2025-03-05 08:00:00 UTC	2025-03-04 11:04:24.198038 U...	103.729999...

Figure 34. Output of the electricity analysis model

4.3.5.1.2.3 Production estimation

This section describes the production analysis model, which corresponds to the following block in the Forecast architecture:

Figure 35. Production analysis model

Based on the work described in Annex 0, a model that estimates the potential production as a function of the meteorological conditions and past production history has been implemented. The following data is used as input:

date	operating_time	production_mass	weather_id	weather_type	precipitation_probab	precipitation_id	precipitation_intensity
2025-02-21	0.0	0.0	7	Light showers/rain	100.0	1	Weak
2025-02-24	10.67	5359.621999999...	5	Cloudy (High cloud)	0.0	0	No precipitation
2025-02-25	10.41	4871.363	3	Sunny intervals	25.0	0	No precipitation
2025-02-26	8.39	2732.241	5	Cloudy (High cloud)	0.0	0	No precipitation

Figure 36. Input data for Forecast production model

This table combines production information and operating times, extracted from the data lake, and precipitation data obtained from IPMA. These data are processed and stored in the Data Warehouse before being fed to the model. The model then uses a 30-day window to obtain past production values that coincide with certain precipitation conditions. With this information, it generates a production prediction for the next five days applying the algorithm shown below:

$$day\ efficiency = \frac{production\ mass}{operating\ time}$$

$$efficiency[date] = \frac{day\ efficiency[date]}{\max(day\ efficiency)}$$

The model only takes into account days in which production has been above zero. As new data points are received, the accuracy of the algorithm will increase. The output is stored in a new table in the Data Warehouse to be visualized in Power BI. The following figure shows an example of this output:

Type	Date	Last update	Efficiency
Rain/showers	2025-02-28	2025-02-28 10:50:16.429232 U...	0.333333333333...
Light showers/rain	2025-03-01	2025-02-28 10:50:16.429232 U...	0.333333333333...
Light showers/rain	2025-03-02	2025-02-28 10:50:16.429232 U...	0.333333333333...
Light showers/rain	2025-03-03	2025-02-28 10:50:16.429232 U...	0.333333333333...
Showers/rain	2025-03-04	2025-02-28 10:50:16.429232 U...	0.333333333333...

Figure 37. Output data for Forecast production model.

The service is deployed with Docker-compose and scheduled via cron. It is hosted on Sigma’s infrastructure.

4.3.5.1.3 Service outputs

The outputs of the different models described above is also presented through a series of Power BI dashboards. These dashboards are based on those introduced in past deliverables, adapted to the final DigiEcoQuarry look and feel.

4.3.5.1.3.1 Water consumption dashboard

The water consumption dashboard offers two types of information: weather and air quality in the quarry based on the sensors deployed on the field; and water consumption and consumption estimation. The figure below shows a screenshot of this dashboard:

Figure 38. Water consumption dashboard for Forecast service.

The first graph (top left) displays the dust levels in four different points of the quarry, with threshold-determined colours based on acceptable PM25 levels in the EU (maximum of 20ug/m3).

The second graph (top right) focuses on weather variables. Last recorded values as well as a history is offered for temperature and humidity. Accumulated wind direction and speed is displayed via a wind rose graph. All these variables can be filtered temporarily with the filter bar below.

The water status graph (bottom left) shows information regarding water consumption. On first place, the gauge handle indicates the current water consumption. The gauge itself is graduated according to the recommended consumption in the quarry. The number in red is the output of the water projection model, and shows the estimated water consumption by the end of the year. Lastly, the date displayed in blue indicates when the recommended consumption limit will be reached, according to the past consumption rate.

The last graph (bottom right) also shows water consumption information but focused on the history. The light blue line represents the actual consumption during the year, while the dotted yellow on represents the consumption forecast. The red line indicates the recommended consumption limit.

4.3.5.1.3.2 Energy dashboard

The energy dashboard is focused on the output of the clean energy prediction model. It is composed of two graphs: the first displays the historical energy prices in Portugal. The second offers an indication of when the price is expected to be lower in the coming days (and hence when the energy is coming from in clean sources), to let the quarry operators plan work breaks accordingly: columns represent each of the following five days, and rows represent the working hours of each day.

Figure 39. Energy dashboard for Forecast service.

4.3.5.1.3.3 Production dashboard

The last dashboard is focused on the production part of the service. The first graph provides an overview of the production history of the quarry, obtaining data from the data lake. It is also possible to filter this production for the type of final product. The second one presents the output of the production estimation model. It presents the potential production estimation for the next five days, along with the weather predictions for each day:

Figure 40. Production dashboard for Forecast service.

4.3.6 CSI

This section describes the updates carried out on the anomalies detection service deployed in CSI.

4.3.6.1 Anomalies detection service

This service aims to constantly monitor production equipment at the quarry site (plant or any other machinery) using aerial and contact sensors to record sound and vibrations. Continuous monitoring of the different machines/components should ease the detection of machinery malfunctions or failures and minimise their impact on production. Ultimately, this may be used to develop predictive and prospective maintenance capabilities using external and historical metadata on the individual parts involved.

4.3.6.1.1 Hardware Integration and deployment

The service requires a specific hardware component to capture noise and vibrations at the quarry's, monitor specific equipment's functioning, and generate functioning profiles and alarms. Deliverable D4.3 introduced the architecture of this device, based on a Raspberry Pi:

Figure 41. Architecture of the anomalies detection service.

This device must be placed near the device under test and have access to an AC power connection outlet.

For the deployment the following elements are needed:

- Local network connectivity: from the edge component to the network. Alternatively, the system is devised to avoid needing such components using 4G connectivity.
- Virtual network control connects the individual components with the cloud servers. The service is designed not to require this connection to be operative all day but largely recommends that it happen and that we keep track of it.
- Cloud servers: The whole service is managed by external servers that monitor the individual edge components to which these connect. Those serve the pre-filtered data or get their models updated from the cloud side. Processed and tagged alarms are fired from this specific component.

4.3.6.1.2 Models

The following block diagram in Figure 42 displays the architecture of the final system solution. It shows the different modules that make up the structure of the solution. It shows the parallelism between the audio-guided system (left side of the figure) and the vibration-guided system (right side); their structure will be the same, with the only difference being the type of recordings and the internal parameters of each system. The different modules that can be observed are: Data Acquisition, Data Processing, Storage (the figures representing data storage in the lower corners and the lower middle part of the image), Model Training, Model Evaluation, Alarm Generation (Monitor Alarm), and Real-time Integration (Integrated Decision and/or Model). The Evaluate Models characterise the audio and the vibrations being able to differentiate the different machine characteristics. The Integrated Decision Model is responsible to gather the information processed in both input formats and determines if an abnormal behaviour is detected.

Figure 42. Component Diagram of the failure detection system.

4.3.6.1.3 Service outputs

If a trigger condition is met, different pieces of information are produced. The module shall:

- Fire an alarm to the alarm dashboard.
- Send an abnormal event to the IQS platform, including the type of event, timestamp, module/site unique identifier, and the corresponding raw signal to ease posterior processing. Note that for this task, a minimum delay may exist for the signalled alarm due to signal windowing and overlaps.
- Send the data to the cloud module for storing and posterior evaluation of the sample using more advanced (and computationally heavier) models. These models may also validate the alarm using advanced AI audio models, categorising the event in an informed way. Additionally, the cloud modules may find relevant information by integrating the information from multiple sensors. This holistic approach shall provide a more complete perspective on the quarry operations.

4.4 Challenges and Lessons Learned

4.4.1 Insights from Operational Feedback

- Quality and granulometry services: quarries represent a challenge to deploy hardware in them, due to the harsh conditions that they usually present, especially in terms of dust. Any hardware device must be properly isolated, ideally with IP67 protection or higher. Camera lenses should also be cleaned periodically to maintain proper image quality.
- Stockpile volume calculation service: The service was originally designed to be provided using fixed cameras. The latter after discussions with the quarry managers was rejected and instead the solution using a mobile to record the piles was undertaken. The latter allowed to have a very flexible solution able to handle for example moving stockpiles (this situation is quite common both in Vicat and Holcim).
- Anomalies detection service: The design of a simple and portable hardware solution was well appreciated by the quarry managers since it provides flexibility when using it for different machines that could be in remote locations with respect to the main plant. Moreover, the ability to characterize and detect abnormal functioning in different types of machines is a plus of the solution.
- Forecast: predictive models need very large amounts of data to work properly. Any service of this kind needs to ensure that enough data sources are available to obtain meaningful results. This was an issue to develop an accurate dust model in the quarry. Also as mentioned for the quality and granulometry services, isolating devices from environmental conditions must be a priority for deploying any kind of sensor.
- MetaQuarry: for a service such as MetaQuarry to succeed (that is, to be used by quarry personnel) it is crucial to reduce the friction with the existing infrastructure, integrating it with the document repository used by quarries to avoid having to move or reorganize all documentation.

4.4.2 Recommendations for Future Refinements

- Quality and granulometry services: although these services are able to detect abnormal events, which can be visualized from the Power BI dashboards, a potential improvement would be to make these alarms real time, even connecting them with the quarries' expert systems to automate certain aspects of the operation.
- Stockpile volume calculation service: The parametrization of the recording APP in the mobile is quite complicated and for this reason the design of an ad-hoc APP was planned, the latter will be able to consider by design the needed parameters in the mobile to perform the video recordings. In the near future only one APP will be used to record and also send all the information to the cloud where the volume calculations are performed.
- Anomalies detection service: The models implemented are able to characterise different quarries equipment (Crushers, Sieves, conveyor belts...) but there is a lack of failure datasets. The latter will be obtained as time goes by and failures start to appear while using the recording device. The obtained datasets will help characterize failures and therefore the models will be more precise and will help even more taking maintenance actions decisions, diminishing risks and most probably also reducing repair costs.
- Forecast: as mentioned before, deploying a larger number of sensors would allow for a more accurate dust modelling, which could be integrated in the water consumption service. Besides, a user interface for these sensors would facilitate their configuration.
- MetaQuarry: integrating this service with additional document repositories, such as Dropbox, would increase its potential market.

A general comment is related to the usage of Power BI as a visualization tool. While it has proven to be a very useful tool to create business reports, and it is easily integrated with commercially available solutions, it is not suitable for real-time application. For this reason, other tools, such as Grafana, would be use to visualize data for more real-time oriented service, such as dust monitoring in the Forecast service.

4.5 Conclusions and Recommendations

4.5.1 Summary of Achievements

The different AI services that have been developed have managed to automate quarry process that before were done manually, to increase the level of knowledge about the operation and to improve the efficiency of certain tasks.

The services leverage existing quarry information, new data generated during the project, public sources and ad-hoc sensors to raise the level of digitalization for the project pilots.

4.5.2 Proposed Actions for Future Deployments

Future deployments have to take into account the characteristics of the quarrying industry in order to succeed. It has already been mentioned that quarries are a harsh environment, due to exposure to weather conditions, vibrations and dust, so protection for those conditions is crucial for any hardware deployed in a quarry.

It is also important to consider that minimizing downtime is usually a priority for quarries. It is then important to plan the deployments accordingly, ensuring that the impact for the quarry as small as possible.

5 Data warehouse

5.1 Continuous support activities

5.1.1 Stakeholders

The main stakeholders of the Data Warehouse are the users of the AI services. However, data ingestion is handled via a series of pipelines that obtain data from the data lake or the services themselves. Thus, only one user has to be authenticated in the DWH for this task, the one assigned to the pipelines. A service account was created for this process, assigning it the minimum permissions to upload data.

On the other hand, access to the data is handled through Power BI dashboards, so Power BI needs permissions to read data in the DWH. Since not all Power BI users must be able to access all data, different service accounts have been created for each user, with granular access to only the datasets they are involved in.

5.1.2 Monitoring of the DWH

The components involved in the Data Warehouse are monitored in different ways. In first place, periodic queries are performed to analyse the data uploaded, to ensure that it is up-to-date and thus the pipelines are working as intended.

BigQuery also keeps logs, which are checked periodically, to identify potential issues.

Lastly, the usage of the Data Warehouse is also checked periodically, to ensure that it is reasonable according to the expectations.

5.1.3 Maintenance of the DWH

Maintenance tasks for the Data Warehouse have been limited to the creation of new pipelines as new data became available. In some cases, after a significant update in the services, all data for that service has been purged to ensure that all information is relevant.

Other maintenance tasks are delegated to Google, who hosts the Data Warehouse.

5.1.4 Data integration

Data integration is done through the previously-mentioned pipelines, which extract data from relevant sources and store it in the Data Warehouse. These pipelines have been described in deliverable D4.4.

5.2 Issue monitoring and resolution

5.2.1 Process for reporting issues

Issue reporting has been performed in a similar way to the one described in section 4.2.1, prioritizing close contact with stakeholders.

5.2.2 Common issues encountered

The main issues encountered in this period have been related to user permissions. In one instance, due to a problem with Sigma's providers, the accounts that were being used to access the DWH lost permissions. This was solved by Sigma's IT team without any data loss.

Another instance was related to an update to the user roles from Google, which caused the loss of permissions to execute queries that were necessary for the video services. Fortunately, this was also promptly solved after some investigation.

5.2.3 Resolution strategies

Since issues have been mostly internal, they have been resolved thanks to the cooperation between the R&D and IT teams in Sigma. The issue management tool that is in place in the company allows to properly prioritize and tackle these issues.

5.3 Refinements of Data Warehouse

5.3.1 Identification of Refinement Needs

All updates to the Data Warehouse have been related to the creation to new tables to store newly available information and to include Spanish weather data for the Quality service.

5.3.1.1 Architecture revisited

As it has already been mentioned in past deliverables (D4.4, D4.6), the Data Warehouse is in charge of storing business-related historical information. It retrieves data from the data lake and other external sources, aggregates it and stores it in a structured way.

For convenience, the architecture reported in D4.6 is shown below:

Figure 43. Data Warehouse architecture.

This architecture has not undergone any changes since the last report. It still retrieves data from the data lake (CDMP for general quarry information and data lake browser for sensor data), and external sources: IPMA for Portugal weather data, OMIE for electricity prices and from a local weather station to complement IPMA’s and sensor data.

Once structured and stored, this information is made available to Power BI through BigQuery’s native integration with the business intelligence tool.

5.3.1.2 Interfaces

The Data Warehouse interacts with the data lake and external sources, such as IPMA or OMIE, to retrieve data, and with Power BI to visualize these data. The interfaces used to communicate with these components have been described in deliverable D4.4 and D4.6 and remain largely unchanged.

One small addition has been the obtention of weather data in Valdilecha (Madrid), where CEMEX’s quarry is located, to complement the information provided by the quality service. This information is retrieved via a public API offered by the Spanish website *el-tiempo.net*, which interacts with AEMET:

<https://www.el-tiempo.net/api/json/v2/provincias/28/municipios/28165>,

where “*provincias*” references the province of interest (Madrid, with code 28) and “*municipios*” refers to the municipality, in this case, Valdilecha, with code 28165.

This information is displayed directly in Power BI, in the quality service dashboard.

5.3.1.3 Tables

As described in deliverables D4.4 and D4.6, the information stored in the Data Warehouse is structured in tables. This section describes the remaining tables that have been created for those data that were still missing. The process to create these tables have been detailed in the deliverables mentioned before.

5.3.1.3.1 Production

This table stores information regarding production mass in CIMPOR’s quarry, as reported by ARCO’s weighing system, as well as the output of the production forecast service:

Aggregate_production		Production_efficiency_forecast	
string	date	string	date
float	productionMass	float	efficiency
		string	last_update
		string	type

Figure 44. Production tables in Data Warehouse.

5.3.1.3.2 Electricity prices

This table stores information about electricity prices in Portugal, obtained through OMIE, as well as the output of the electricity price forecast service:

Electricity_prices		Electricity_price_forecast	
string	date	string	date
float	price	int	day
		int	hour
		string	last_update
		float	price

Figure 45. Electricity tables in Data Warehouse.

5.4 Challenges and Lessons Learned

5.4.1 Insights from Operational Feedback

BigQuery has proven to be an adequate tool for developing a Data Warehouse. It is easy to store and organize information and to integrate it with external tools. It also has good security measurements in place.

The usage of the data lake as a centralized data point has also eased the task of gathering the required information for the services.

5.4.2 Recommendations for Future Refinements

A potential improvement for the Data Warehouse would be to implement automatic error detection in the input data pipelines, to ensure that all data stored is valid.

Automating the pipeline creation process would also ease the input of new data.

5.5 Conclusions and Recommendations

5.5.1 Summary of Achievements

The Data Warehouse has successfully served its purpose of providing a central point for storing business information. It aggregates data from different sources and makes it available for additional services.

It has been integrated with the rest of the IQS infrastructure, thanks to the usage of standardized interfaces and data formats.

5.5.2 Proposed Actions for Future Deployments

Future deployments must carefully consider the amount of data that is being processed, in order to correctly dimension the data warehouse tool.

Besides, automating the pipeline deployment and update process would improve the availability and ease of maintenance of the system.

6 BIM

6.1 Continuous support activities

6.1.1 Stakeholders

The BIM integration process involved collaboration with multiple stakeholders across the DigiEcoQuarry ecosystem. Key stakeholders included quarry site managers, operational teams, IT departments, and data providers from WP3. Ongoing engagement with these stakeholders was essential to ensure that the BIM implementation aligned with operational requirements and user expectations. Regular communication channels were established to gather feedback, address concerns, and provide updates on system improvements.

6.1.2 Monitoring of the BIM components

Continuous monitoring of the BIM components was implemented to ensure system performance and data integrity. This included regular checks of model integrity, data synchronization status, and user interface functionality. Monitoring activities were conducted on a weekly basis, with more comprehensive performance assessments performed monthly. The monitoring process helped identify potential issues before they impacted operational use and provided valuable insights for ongoing system improvements.

6.1.3 Maintenance of the BIM components

Maintenance activities for the BIM system included regular updates to the CDE platform, refinement of data connections, and optimization of model performance. The maintenance schedule was aligned with operational requirements to minimize disruption, with most activities conducted during low-usage periods. Documentation of all maintenance activities was maintained to ensure traceability and facilitate knowledge transfer among technical teams.

6.1.4 Data integration

Data integration activities focused on maintaining and improving connections between the BIM models and various data sources, primarily through the data lake. The integration process was refined over time to improve data synchronization efficiency and reduce latency. Regular validation of integrated data was conducted to ensure accuracy and completeness, with correction procedures implemented when discrepancies were identified.

6.2 Issue monitoring and resolution

6.2.1 Process for reporting issues

A structured process for reporting BIM-related issues was established to ensure timely resolution and effective communication. Users could report issues through a dedicated email address (deq@app-consultoria.com) or through designated site contacts. All reported issues were logged in a tracking system, categorized by severity and type, and assigned to appropriate technical resources. Regular status updates were provided to issue reporters, and resolution timelines were established based on issue severity.

6.2.2 Common issues encountered

Several common issues were encountered during the BIM implementation and operation:

- Data synchronization delays between the data lake and CDE.
- Model loading performance in areas with complex geometry or numerous assets.
- User authentication and access control challenges.
- Visualization inconsistencies across different client devices.
- Occasional misalignment between model elements and associated data.

These issues were documented along with their resolution approaches to build a knowledge base for future reference.

6.2.3 Resolution strategies

Resolution strategies were developed for each category of issue, with emphasis on both immediate fixes and long-term preventive measures. For data synchronization issues, optimized data transfer protocols were implemented and monitoring alerts were established. Model performance challenges were addressed through geometry optimization and incremental loading techniques. User access issues were resolved through improved authentication workflows and clearer permission structures. Each resolution was documented and incorporated into the overall system improvement roadmap.

6.3 Refinements of BIM System

6.3.1 Identification of Refinement Needs

Through ongoing monitoring and user feedback, several key areas for BIM tool refinement were identified:

- Need for simplified asset classification to enhance data navigation.
- Requirements for more intuitive data visualization dashboards.
- Opportunities to improve model integration with operation planning tools.
- Enhancement of performance for large model handling.
- Refinement of user interface elements to improve accessibility.

These identified needs guided the subsequent refinement efforts across all pilot sites, ensuring that the BIM integration aligned more closely with operational requirements and user expectations.

6.3.2 Holcim

For the Holcim Pioltello San Bovio site, refinements focused primarily on production data visualization. Given the site's unique operational characteristics centred around dredging operations, the visualization dashboards were customized to highlight relevant production metrics. The 3D model was optimized to better represent the underwater extraction areas, providing more meaningful context for the production data.

Key refinements included:

- Implementation of production-focused dashboards.
- Optimization of model geometry to improve loading performance.
- Enhanced filtering capabilities to support comparative analysis across different time periods.
- Integration of simplified topographic representations to provide context for production data.

Figure 46. Pioltello San Bovio: CDE Production Data.

6.3.3 Vicat

At the Vicat Fenouillet site, refinements targeted the integration between the BIM model and the maintenance planning tools. Following the implementation of the 4D maintenance planning approach and mobile app, the BIM tools were enhanced to provide visual context for maintenance activities and equipment status.

Specific refinements included:

- Development of specialized asset status visualization linked to maintenance data.
- Implementation of color-coding schemes to indicate maintenance priorities.
- Creation of saved views aligned with regular inspection routes.
- Enhancement of component identification systems to match maintenance checklist terminology.
- Optimization of mobile device performance for field-based access.

Figure 47. CDE: 3D Model Element related static data.

6.3.4 Cemex

For the Cemex Valdilecha site, refinements focused on enhancing the integration of production data, consumption metrics, and mobile machinery information. The system was adapted to provide more comprehensive visualization of the relationship between extraction activities and processing operations.

Key refinements included:

- Implementation of energy consumption visualization linked to specific plant components.
- Enhancement of material flow visualization within the treatment plant.
- Integration of mobile machinery data with spatial context for improved route visualization.
- Development of customized dashboards highlighting production efficiency metrics.
- Optimization of data.

Figure 47. CDE as a Digital Twin. Connection with external data.

6.3.5 Cimpor

At the Cimpor Agrepor-Alenquer site, refinements emphasized improving the mobile machinery data integration and supporting the visualization of extraction planning. The 3D model was enhanced to better represent the extraction zones, providing spatial context for the mobile machinery performance data.

Specific refinements included:

- Enhancement of equipment cycle visualization with spatial context.
- Integration of extraction volume data with equipment performance metrics.
- Implementation of customized filters for equipment type and operational area.
- Optimization of model geometry to improve performance in extraction zone visualization.
- Development of specialized dashboards for equipment efficiency analysis.

Figure 48. Fenouillet: CDE Streams. Consumption Data.

6.4 Challenges and Lessons Learned

6.4.1 Insights from Operational Feedback

Through operational feedback and user experience evaluation, several key insights were gained:

- The importance of aligning BIM asset classification with existing operational terminology to facilitate user adoption.
- The need for balanced data visualization that provides comprehensive insights without overwhelming users with excessive detail.
- The value of integrating real-time data with contextual information to support meaningful decision-making.
- The importance of flexible implementation approaches that can adapt to varying levels of data availability across different sites.
- The critical role of user training and support in maximizing the value of BIM integration.

These insights highlighted the need for both technical excellence and practical usability in BIM implementation, with particular emphasis on adapting sophisticated technologies to the specific operational context of quarry environments.

6.4.2 Recommendations for Future Refinements

Based on the challenges encountered and lessons learned, several recommendations for future refinements have been identified:

- Develop more standardized approaches to asset classification and identification to facilitate cross-site data comparison.
- Enhance data synchronization capabilities to support more frequent updates and improve real-time monitoring.
- Strengthen the integration between BIM models and operational planning tools to provide more comprehensive decision support.
- Implement more intuitive user interfaces with customizable dashboards to meet varying user needs and preferences.
- Develop more comprehensive training materials and support resources to accelerate user adoption and maximize system utilization.
- Explore opportunities for mobile-optimized interfaces to support field-based data access and decision support.

6.5 Conclusions and Recommendations

6.5.1 Summary of Achievements

The BIM integration implementation has successfully established a foundation for enhanced data visibility and operational monitoring across all pilot sites. Key achievements include:

- Successful development and implementation of comprehensive 3D models for all pilot sites.
- Integration of various data types from the data lake, including production metrics, consumption data, and equipment performance.
- Development of customized visualization tools that support operational decision-making.
- Establishment of connections between physical assets and operational data.
- Implementation of a flexible system architecture that accommodates different site requirements.
- Creation of a platform that demonstrates the potential for digital transformation in the quarrying sector.

These achievements have provided valuable insights into the practical application of BIM technologies in quarry environments, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities of digital integration in this sector.

6.5.2 Proposed Actions for Future Deployments

For future deployments of BIM integration in quarry environments, several key actions are proposed:

- Establish standardized modelling and data integration protocols early in the implementation process.
- Implement more comprehensive user needs assessment to guide system design and customization.
- Develop more robust data validation procedures to ensure accuracy and reliability of integrated information.
- Implement phased deployment approaches that allow for iterative refinement and user adaptation.
- Establish dedicated training and support resources to ensure effective user adoption.
- Develop more comprehensive documentation and knowledge transfer procedures.
- Explore opportunities for integration with additional operational systems, such as maintenance management and inventory control.
- Investigate the potential for predictive analytics based on integrated operational data.

These proposed actions would enhance the effectiveness of future BIM implementations in quarry environments, building on the lessons learned from the DigiEcoQuarry project experience.

7 Conclusions

7.1 Summary of Achievements

Regarding the current IQS architecture, all data are actionable, meaning that the data collected and processed within the system can be effectively utilized for decision-making and operational improvements or reused by another system.

The successful integration of IQS into the quarry ecosystem was made possible through the accurate definition of data models and the creation of a common data format. This approach facilitated interfacing with expert systems and enabled the efficient management and utilization of as much quarry data as possible. It ensured seamless data exchange and interoperability, thereby maximizing the value derived from quarry data.

As for the AI services, they have been updated and refined according to the needs of the project pilots. The main achievements are summarized below:

- Quality and granulometry services: development and deployment of a computer vision service able to analyse material quality, size, belt occupation and identify potentially dangerous rock fragments. The service includes vision hardware, image processing algorithms and visualization dashboards.
 - Stockpile volume calculation service: development of a service able to determine the volume of product stockpiles, through the recording of said stockpiles with a mobile application. The service includes the development of the mobile application and processing algorithms.
 - Anomalies detection service: development of a service able to detect abnormal behaviour in quarry machinery through the analysis of sound and vibrations. This service involves the development of a piece of hardware to gather sound and vibrations and the processing algorithms.
 - Forecast service: development of a service able to leverage existing data and generate additional ones to make forecasts about variables of interest, in this case, water consumption, clean energy consumption and production efficiency. The service involves the deployment of dust, water and wind sensors, and the development of connectors to obtain data from the IQS and additional sources, as well as the algorithms in charge of processing these data and the dashboards to visualize it.
 - MetaQuarry: development of a system able to retrieve documents and information within documents through natural language queries. The system is able to access information in private clouds, Microsoft Teams and Google Drive.

Besides, a Data Warehouse, focused on storing business-related information and integrated with the remaining IQS infrastructure has been successfully developed.

The implementation of BIM integration within the project has delivered several significant achievements that enhance operational visibility and decision-making capabilities across the pilot sites:

- Comprehensive Digital Representation: Development and deployment of detailed 3D models for all pilot sites, providing accurate digital representations of treatment plants, terrain surfaces, and operational assets.
- Industry-Standard Integration: Successful implementation of IFC-based model exchange, ensuring interoperability and establishing a foundation for future BIM applications in the quarrying sector.
- Operational Data Visualization: Creation of customized dashboards that connect physical assets with real-time operational data, enabling intuitive monitoring of production metrics, consumption data, and equipment performance.
- 4D Planning Implementation: Development of time-based planning tools that enhance visualization of quarry lifecycle processes, supporting better resource allocation and operational sequencing.

- Maintenance Management Enhancement: Integration of preventive maintenance systems with visual asset representation, particularly at the Vicat site, improving maintenance planning and execution through visual context.
- Mobile Application Support: Implementation of field-based data access through mobile applications, enabling on-site teams to record and access critical information directly linked to digital assets.
- Cross-System Data Exchange: Establishment of robust connections with the data lake, enabling seamless integration with other DigiEcoQuarry components and demonstrating the value of unified data architectures in quarry environments.

These achievements collectively demonstrate the potential of BIM technologies to transform traditional quarry management approaches, providing a foundation for enhanced operational efficiency and decision support across the quarry lifecycle.

7.2 Proposed Actions for Future Deployments

To ensure the success of future deployments of the IQS, several actions are recommended. Finalizing the specification of key indicators is essential, as completing the definition of certain indicators will enable more accurate decision-making. Automating deployment phases is crucial, as increasing automation in deployment processes supports continuous integration and reduces manual efforts. Additionally, expanding IQS capabilities is important. This involves extending the system's functionality by incorporating new datasets commonly provided by companies' Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, such as SAP. Once the new datasets are identified, new connectors can be implemented, and additional dashboards created to enhance system insights.

Several actions have been identified as potential improvements in future deployments. For instance, for the quality and granulometry services, making the events they generate real time or connecting them with the quarries' expert systems to automate certain aspects of the operation would improve the usefulness of the solution. The Forecast service, on the other hand, would benefit from having a larger number of sensors deployed, which would enable more accurate dust modelling. For MetaQuarry, integrating this service with additional document repositories, such as Dropbox, would increase its potential market.

Based on the experience gained through the DigiEcoQuarry project implementation, several key actions are proposed for future BIM deployments in quarry environments:

- Standardized Modelling Protocols: Establish consistent modelling standards specifically adapted for quarry environments, including asset classification systems and level of detail requirements to ensure uniformity across implementations.
- Early Stakeholder Engagement: Implement comprehensive stakeholder analysis and engagement processes at project initiation to better align technical capabilities with operational requirements.
- Phased Implementation Approach: Adopt a staged deployment methodology that allows for iterative refinement and gradual user adaptation, beginning with core functionality and expanding to more advanced features.
- Enhanced Training Resources: Develop comprehensive training materials and support resources tailored to various user roles, including simplified guides for operational staff and more detailed documentation for technical teams.
- Data Validation Framework: Implement robust data validation procedures to ensure accuracy and reliability of integrated information before visualization in the BIM environment.
- Real-Time Data Optimization: Enhance synchronization mechanisms to support more frequent data updates for time-sensitive operational monitoring and decision support.
- Mobile-Optimized Interfaces: Develop dedicated mobile applications that provide streamlined access to critical information for field-based teams, with offline capabilities for areas with limited connectivity.

- Integration Expansion: Explore opportunities for integration with additional operational systems, such as maintenance management, inventory control, and enterprise resource planning.
- Analytics Enhancement: Implement predictive analytics capabilities that leverage historical operational data to forecast maintenance needs, production capacities, and resource requirements.
- Deployment Automation: Create streamlined deployment procedures and documentation to facilitate faster implementation and configuration in new environments.

These proposed actions aim to enhance the effectiveness and value of future BIM implementations in quarry environments, building on the lessons learned through the DigiEcoQuarry project experience.

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Annex I

Detail of crusher model for Quality determination service

The crusher model has the goal of analysing the occupation and size of rock fragments found in the primary crusher. This involves segmenting the image into two categories: background and foreground. Deep learning approaches have achieved significant advances in this field. However, these methods are typically designed for fully supervised learning, making the generation of segmentation masks time-consuming and resource-intensive. Recently, Weakly-Supervised Image Segmentation (WSIS) methods have emerged as a potential solution to reduce the reliance on detailed pixel-level annotations. While WSIS can expedite the annotation process, it often struggles to achieve the accuracy required for high-quality pixel-level segmentation.

Therefore, the chosen approach acknowledges the need for hand-made annotations to achieve the desired segmentation quality. The objective is to minimize the reliance on these hand-made annotations while obtaining the best possible segmentation results from a minimal number of images with high-quality annotations.

With this in mind, the pipeline shown in Figure 10 was designed to train a segmentation model. The pipeline integrates multiple stages to achieve high-quality image segmentation with minimal human annotations. The process begins with a set of pre-processed input images. The data is used to train a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to model the background. The reconstructed backgrounds facilitate the computation of pseudo-labels, serving as an initial approximation of the foreground regions. These pseudo-labels initiate the training of a U-Net segmentation model. To further refine the model's performance, a small set of highly representative images is annotated with high-quality masks using the SAM model. Data augmentation techniques are applied to this high-quality set and incorporated into the U-Net's fine-tuning process. The procedure iteratively fine-tunes the model, incorporating feedback from task-specific training to improve generalization. During this phase, segmentation masks generated for specific tasks are analysed and used to refine the model's performance. The human-in-the-loop between task-specific training and fine-tuning ensures continuous improvement in segmentation accuracy.

This approach can be described in two steps:

- 1) Generation of a robust initial training set, using pseudo labels created through preprocessing techniques and a background model based on VAE to address environmental variability.
- 2) Creation of a pipeline that combines pseudo-labelling, manual refinement, and data augmentation to achieve high-quality segmentation from a U-Net with minimal annotations.

The result of this process is a segmented image without background shown in Figure 11.

Pseudolabel generation and background removal

The backgrounds exhibit high variability and diverse spurious effects due to dust, varying light conditions, and uneven colour and texture. This means a challenge for segmentation, leading to over-segmentation and under-segmentation. Thus, preprocessing steps are applied to the images to mitigate these issues. These steps aim at enhancing the contrast between the foreground and background, reduce noise, increase the visibility of gaps between ore fragments, and normalize image characteristics to minimize the impact of climatic variations and light flares.

The preprocessing starts by converting the colour image to grayscale to reduce the computational complexity by compressing the three-channel RGB image into a single channel, also highlighting the contrast between the image's foreground and background, crucial for segmentation.

Next, the grayscale image undergoes standardization to normalize the intensity distribution, ensuring that the data conforms to a consistent range, reducing variations caused by lighting or acquisition conditions.

Following standardization, Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) is applied to enhance local contrast further and highlight fine details in the darker regions of the image. This technique not only suppresses noise but also improves the visibility of key features, such as the boundaries between ore fragments.

Finally, gamma adjustment is performed to refine the brightness levels, making subtle image details more prominent. The following figure shows the original image together with the result of the different preprocessing steps:

Figure 46. Stepwise results of the Pre-processing pipeline. From left to right: original, grey scale, standardized, CLAHE and gamma-adjusted

Together, these steps ensure the input data is optimized for downstream analysis and segmentation tasks.

After preprocessing, the background needs to be removed. As mentioned before, although the background is mostly static, it consists of continuously rotating rollers. Being an outdoor environment, the background is affected by climatic conditions, changes in illumination, seasonal variations, glare, shadows, and other factors such as dust, as shown in Figure 47:

Figure 47. Examples of background variability across different times, weather conditions, and seasonal changes.

For this reason, classical mathematical models, such as Median, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM), have failed to effectively capture the full range of environmental variability in the images, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 48. Comparison of background removal techniques using classical mathematical models. From left to right: original, median, KNN, GMM

To address the limitations of classical background removal methods, a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) has been trained to model the background and climatic conditions, providing a reference image for identifying and removing spurious effects.

The VAE uses an encoder-decoder architecture, where the encoder extracts hierarchical features from the input image and maps them to a latent space. The decoder mirrors the encoder structure using transposed convolutional layers to up sample the latent vector back to the original resolution.

To train the VAE, a dataset was constructed, composed exclusively of images containing only the background (weakly-supervised learning). These images are captured during non-operational hours of the quarry, such as rest periods and non-working days. The dataset includes images taken at different times of the day and across all seasons to account for the natural variability in environmental conditions. Training the VAE on this comprehensive dataset allows the model to generalize across weather, lighting, and seasonal changes.

The VAE generates a reconstructed version of a given input image. The difference between the input image and the VAE-reconstructed background (shown in Figure 49) is then used to identify foreground objects.

Figure 49. VAE-based background removal

This reconstructed background is then used to generate low-quality annotation masks. These masks are used to capture object regions with varying detail and noise levels and are essential for weakly supervised learning, where precise annotations are unavailable.

The mask generation process begins with the absolute difference between the input and reconstructed background. This difference highlights regions where the VAE fails to reproduce the background, typically corresponding to foreground objects. Next, the pixel-wise difference between the original image and its VAE-reconstructed background is computed for each image. To mitigate illumination effects, the background is normalized to match the mean and standard deviation of the input image for non-black pixels. The absolute difference is obtained, serving as the foundation for mask extraction. Different techniques are then used to generate masks, such as Gaussian Blurred Difference or Dilation-Enhanced Difference. Examples of these masks can be found in the figure below.

Figure 50. Mask generation techniques: Gaussian Blurred Difference (left) and Dilation-Enhanced Difference (right)

Segmentation model training

The next step is the segmentation of the image. For this task, a U-Net architecture has been used. The U-Net model (Ronneberger et al., 2015) is a fully convolutional network extensively used in segmentation tasks similar to the one at hand. Its architecture consists of a symmetric encoder-decoder structure optimized for precise localization, making it highly effective for pixel-level predictions.

To ensure efficient retraining and evaluation of the model, a representative subset of 50 images was selected from the entire dataset of 81,000 images. To facilitate a faster and more robust annotation process, the CVAT tool in conjunction with the SAM model were used, with the latter generating initial segmentation masks for the ore, and with annotators refining the masks at a pixel level to achieve high-quality annotations.

Then, the segmentation model is initialized and trained for 100 epochs. Following this initialization, the fine-tuning process was performed using the high-quality annotations, enabling the refinement of the model and achieving its final optimized weights.

To further increase the precision of the model, task-specific fine-tuning was implemented, following two methodologies: one based on the Human-in-the-Loop paradigm and another fully automated approach. Focusing on improving the segmentation of large rocks to detect them more reliably, the procedure starts by applying OpenCV operations to the masks generated by the model. Subsequently, an area-measuring function is used to calculate the sizes of all detected elements within the mask, and the images that contain at least one large rock are identified by applying a predefined threshold.

In the fully automated approach, a bounding box is generated around the region corresponding to the area that exceeded the threshold. This bounding box is then passed to the SAM (Segment Anything Model) framework, which refines the segmentation of the large rock. The refined mask is combined with the original mask to create a more accurate dataset.

In the second methodology, human annotators manually refine the segmentation masks for large rocks instead of using SAM after the model has processed them. These corrected masks are used to retrain the model. This process can be repeated iteratively, as is typical in a Human-in-the-Loop workflow.

The following figure shows an example of the result of these two approaches:

Figure 51. Examples of the annotation process: original image (left), initial segmentation mask produced by SAM (middle), and final annotated image after human refinement (right)

Detail of C3 model for Quality determination service

Dataset generation

The capture of images is carried out through a camera placed directly above the conveyor belt. This positioning was essential to capture a clear and consistent view of the moving objects for accurate data collection.

A critical aspect of the data capture process was ensuring an accurate pixel-to-millimetre conversion, as precise measurements were required for model training. To achieve this, a calibration procedure was conducted to establish a reliable spatial reference. The calibration dataset included objects of known dimensions and distinct colours, which served as ground truth for size estimation. Additionally, a checkerboard pattern was incorporated into the calibration process to facilitate geometric corrections and improve the accuracy of spatial mappings.

The camera was installed under a protective covering to shield it from environmental factors and positioned at a slight angle facing the conveyor belt. This orientation was selected to optimize the field of view while maintaining image clarity. However, it is important to highlight a limitation of this setup: due to the convex shape of the conveyor belt and the inherent 2D perspective of the camera, objects located on the lower, inward-curving sections of the belt remain obscured from view. This occlusion presents challenges in capturing a comprehensive visual record of all materials on the belt.

In summary, the data production pipeline was designed with careful consideration of camera placement, calibration for spatial accuracy, and light and dust protection. Despite the physical and optical constraints imposed by the conveyor belt's geometry, this setup provided a robust framework for collecting high-quality image data for model training and evaluation.

Segmentation and classification model

In this image scenario, the biggest challenge was the classification into two classes (clay and limestone). Limestone was covered from time to time in clay dust when the weather was dryer and in humid clay when the weather was rainier. This was also seen at the conveyor belt's background. Two main challenges were found: one linked to the colour and one related to the size. An initial study was done regarding the geometrical separation between clay and limestone. The initial hypothesis was that clay conglomerates tend to be rounder than limestone rocks which are more angled and rectilinear due to their fracture properties. With this intuition, a measurement of how a physical object occupied space was required, the metrics selected were the fractal dimension of the 2D segmentation mask (Minkowski-Bouligand dimension) and the circularity and the maximum radius. This process is shown in Figure 52: on the left, the lab images are displayed with a manually placed segmentation mask overlayed to each rock, where blue is assigned to the limestone rocks and yellow to the clay conglomerates. On the right-hand side, the bar plots of the fractal dimension, circularity and maximum radius are displayed on the x axis while the frequency is displayed on the y axis. Colour is assigned based on the class: an interesting separation between classes can be seen. This behaviour was not maintained on the real images due to increased complexity on the rock display.

Figure 52. Segmentation masks and metrics for C3 colorimetry

After the initial study with the lab images prior to the final camera placement the results were promising but due to the big differences between lab images and the real images, this classical geometry approaches were discarded for a more novel approach such as a computer vision neural network.

The selected computer vision model was the YOLO V8-SEG (Bolya et al., 2022) (Bolya et al., 2019) (Varghese & M., 2024) model with custom training for multiple-class classification and segmentation. The training, validation and testing data was obtained through a semi-automatic annotation process over the quarry’s images. The annotation criterion was adapted to the real images: since clay conglomerates were difficult to individually spot in the presence of clay dust or wet clay, the segmentation mask was unified as a single instance containing all those clay variations. However, limestone rocks were individually masked due to their geometry and the ability to differentiate one individual rock from another. The following figure shows the confusion matrix for this model:

Figure 53. Confusion matrix per class (Arcilla/Clay, Caliza/Limestone and Background) for the model weights saved at epoch 48 (best validation loss)

It is important to note that there’s still an issue with the differentiation between the background and its incorrect prediction as limestone. This mainly comes from very bright light reflections of the conveyor belt when it has a water cumulus with similar colour and shape properties as the limestone.

Colorimetry analysis

Once the segmentation and the classification of the material is done, a mask over the limestone pixels and another one over the clay pixels are obtained. In the case of the limestone, it will be a polygon mask since the geometry is more concise and defined single instances can be easily separated. For clay, pixels will be a single regular binary mask containing dust particles, clay sand and small clay conglomerates difficult to separate in singular instances.

With pixel-level information, the colorimetry system begins its processing. However, before diving into the system’s workings, it is essential to understand the role of colorimetry in mining and its broader purpose. Accurately classifying colour has always been a challenge for humans due to the subjective nature of colour perception. In the early 20th century, Albert Munsell addressed this issue by inventing and patenting the Munsell colour charts (Munsell, 1906). This

standardized system provides an objective framework for defining and communicating colours based on three parameters: hue (the basic colour), value (the intensity of lightness of the colour), and chroma (the brightness of the colour). In 1941, the first Munsell soil colour charts (MSCs) were released by the U.S. Soil Survey (Donnelly Rice, 1941) (Simonson, 1993). Since then, the MSCs became widely used in geological, agricultural, and environmental fields. These charts enabled consistent and precise soil colour classification, which is crucial for understanding soil composition, formation processes, and environmental conditions. Each soil sample is matched against the standardized colour chips, allowing researchers to document soil properties consistently across different locations and studies. The colour of mining materials often reflects their mineral composition, oxidation states, and weathering processes. For instance:

1. Reddish and yellowish hues often indicate the presence of iron oxides, which can signal the degree of oxidation and environmental exposure.
2. Gray or greenish colours may suggest reducing conditions or the presence of sulphides, which are important in identifying ore deposits.
3. Dark organic-rich soils can reveal areas with higher organic content, often linked to past biological activity or recent deposition.

With the camera system in place, it was necessary to digitally replicate the process of identifying material colours by associating them with the corresponding Munsell Soil Color Chart. To achieve an accurate Munsell colour representation, a series of conversions were required, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 54. Munsell soil chart approximation procedure from the segmentation and classification output

Once the segmentation, classification and the colorimetry are done for every picture captured with the camera, a JSON file is generated containing the information relative to the timestamp of each picture. This way there is a daily record with a summary of all the images analysed during that day's production.

Detail of the Granulometry service model

This section describes the models in charge of estimating the granulometry of the 4/20 product belt. The process starts with the creation of a high-quality training data set for the model, from the images captured by the camera. A critical aspect of the data capture process was ensuring an accurate pixel-to-millimetre conversion. This was achieved by conducting a calibration procedure to establish a reliable spatial reference. The calibration dataset included objects of known dimensions and distinct colours, which served as ground truth for size estimation, as shown in the image below:

Figure 55. Images for calibration dataset

The next step is the segmentation of the images, which is necessary to determine the size of the different fragments. It was opted to create a segmentation mask over all the pixels of each individual rock, since this approach proved to be more precise than other solutions, such as bounding boxes or single-point detection. Several models were studied: DexiNed (Soria et al., 2023), FastSAM (Zhao et al., 2023), YOLOWorld (Cheng et al., 2024) and Yolo8seg (Bolya et al., 2019).

As was the case with the granulometry service in the C3 belt, this setup has the same limitation: due to the convex shape of the conveyor belt and the inherent 2D perspective of the camera, objects located on the lower, inward-curving sections of the belt remain obscured from view. This occlusion presents challenges in capturing a comprehensive visual record of all materials on the belt. This limitation was addressed, on one hand, by cropping the images before applying the segmentation model, as shown in Figure 56. On the other hand, the UPM-AI team conducted several manual measurements on known samples, which were later used to adjust the segmentation results.

Figure 56. a) Full image inference result in a limited number of segmentations c) due to yolo architecture constraints, to overcome this a 4 sized crop is performed in b) for avoiding this limitation and resulting in much better segmentations, like in d)

With the images segmented, the granulometry needs to be determined. This is done by translating blob sizes from pixel to millimetres, to cluster rocks into the different sized sieves. Three different strategies were applied to cluster the fragments: measuring the longest side, the shortest and the area, as shown in Figure 18.

Data analysis for water consumption model in Forecast service

The starting point for this part of the service was the analysis of the dust data captured by the sensors deployed in Alenquer. First, the different measured PM ranges (PM1, PM2.5 and PM10) were compared amongst themselves. It was observed that concentration peaks for all ranges coincide in time, but not in intensity, as the following figure shows:

Figure 57. Dust peaks comparison

The next step was to try to find a relationship between the dust levels and the weather conditions. No correlation was found in variables such as temperature or solar radiation. With wind intensity and accumulated precipitation (shown in Figure 58), it was observed that the dust levels decrease as wind or precipitation increases, but no linear relationship was found.

Figure 58. Wind speed and accumulated precipitation vs. dust

Fitting with a non-linear polynomial was also considered, but the presence of so many outliers would probably produce an overfitting of the model.

On the other hand, high-density dust events have been detected, as shown in Figure 59, although it has not been possible to determine the root cause for them with the available data. This is complicated even further by the fact that some of these events occur out of the working times of the quarry.

Figure 59. High-density dust events

During these high-density events, it was also observed that there are large differences between PM1, PM10 and PM2.5, with PM10 density being the highest, and PM1 being the smallest.

Being able to find meaningful correlations, it was theorized that the distance between the available weather stations and quarry was too big, causing that the measurements were not precise enough. For this reason, it was decided to install an anemometer in the quarry.

This newly acquired wind data were also cross-referenced with the dust information:

Figure 60. Local wind speed (left) and direction (right) vs. dust

Unfortunately, like before, it was observed that the dust levels decreased with higher wind intensities, but no other correlation was found. Something similar occurs with the wind direction: higher concentrations are observed in certain directions, but the possible causes are too many to determine the root one.

Indeed, these results are coherent with the findings of (Sairanen & Rinne, 2019), who tried to model the dust emissions in different quarries. They state:

“Decreasing concentration with increasing wind speed was observed in Quarries 3, in 4 on the second measurement day and in 5 on the first measurement day. An opposite result was observed in Quarry 5 on the second measurement day. Other quarries showed no correlation between wind speed and dust mass.

[...]

Beside differences in crushing circuits and production capacities, different weather conditions during measurements appeared in different quarries, which further complicates the reliability of these findings.”

Thus, it was concluded that, in order to have an accurate dust model, a larger number of sensors should be deployed. A potential line of work would be to develop a model to determine the optimal position of sensors in the quarry, and apply finite element methods (FEM) to model the dust.

Under these circumstances, it was opted to monitor directly the water consumption in the quarry, for which two water counters were installed. Analysing the data they captured, it was observed that the water consumption follows a quite linear curve. For instance, the figure below shows the consumption during most of the year 2024 (units are pulses, 10 pulses equal one cubic meter):

Figure 61. Water consumption in Alenquer during 2024

As the graph shows, the water consumption is piecewise linear. It was decided, then, to implement a regressive model that considers the previous two months of data to predict the future consumption. This model is detailed in the following section. The information gathered by the dust sensors and anemometer is directly displayed in the dashboard along with the water prediction, to give an overview of the quarry conditions and to be able to historically compare this information with consumption data.

Data analysis for the clean energy prediction model in Forecast service

The following data analysis has been performed on weather data obtained through IPMA (Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera; Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere) and electricity prices obtained through OMIE (Operador del Mercado Ibérico Español; Iberian Market Operator). The data acquisition process has been detailed in deliverables D4.4 and D4.6.

Analysing the correlation between electricity prices and three weather variables: wind speed, accumulated precipitation or rain and solar radiation.

A database was built with the electricity price in Portugal and the three mentioned weather variables at every hour during the period 15 December 2023 - 27 March 2024 in every weather station of Portugal. This database was analysed to find correlations between the price and the weather variables **on every Portuguese weather station** as follows:

At a given wind speed in the weather station, the electricity price in Portugal could have taken different values on different hours along the mentioned period. Those different electricity prices are the green dots in Figure 62. At each given wind speed in the weather station, we calculated the average electricity price. That average is the red line in Figure 62. We can notice a **significant correlation between the average electricity price and the wind speed**: As the wind speed increases, the average electricity price decreases in an approximate linear manner, reaching a zero value for wind speeds larger than 12 m/s.

Figure 62. Electricity Price in Portugal as a function of the wind speed

The average electricity price vs the wind speed was also fitted (the blue line in Figure 62) obtaining the coefficient of determination, R^2 . This fitting was performed for every Portuguese station. Figure 62 shows the results of the weather station with the best R^2 , for wind speed, among all the Portuguese weather stations, the so called 'best station'. For wind speed the best station was 'Bragança Aeródromo' (See Figure 62). The fitted blue line is a polynomial of second degree respect to the wind speed:

$$AEP(w) = a_0 + a_1 * w + a_2 * w^2,$$

where AEP is the average electricity price and w is the wind speed.

This **average electricity price-wind speed correlation** is very important, because it allows to make reliable predictions of the average electricity price one or several days ahead: knowing the predicted wind speed for the next days, the function $AEP(w)$ plotted in Figure 62 (the blue line in that figure) can be used to predict the average electricity price for the next days. This process will be very useful for the managers of the quarry in order to **make decisions** to save money.

This correlation is well known and is broadly discussed in the scientific literature. For example, (Mulder & Scholtens, 2013) determined that from certain levels of renewable energy, electricity prices might increasingly be driven by weather conditions, mostly wind intensity. Weather forecasts are used in north European countries by the energy traders who buy and sell electricity contracts in the day-ahead market, using temperature and wind strength as the two key variables when making their decisions (Idsø et al., 2024), in Italy (Casula et al., 2020) highlighted a non-trivial dependency structure between the wind speed series and the electricity price. (Conte & Oliveira, 2024) forecasted the electricity prices and wind speeds in Brazil by using artificial neural networks (ANNs) with genetic algorithms (GAs), and (Rezaei et al., 2022) modelled the electricity prices in Iran by Gated Recurrent Units.

Figure 63. Electricity Price in Portugal as a function of the accumulated precipitation

The same process was performed for the accumulated precipitation or rain (see Figure 63) and for the solar radiation (see Figure 64). No correlation was found between the average electricity price and those two weather variables.

Figure 64. Electricity Price in Portugal as a function of the solar radiation

The same process was performed for the electricity price vs. the wind speed aggregating all the stations together. In this case, a correlation was also found, but the coefficient of determination was $R^2= 0.8488$, smaller than the coefficient of determination obtained with the ‘best station’, the Bragança Aeródromo, $R^2= 0.9495$. Hence, the results using the individual and best station were better.

A further analysis was carried out. The original analysis was performed taking into account all hours (the 24 hours of a day). However, the work in a quarry takes place during daylight hours and working days. Hence, the process was repeated excluding the night and weekend hours (see Figure 65). There is a correlation between the electricity price and the wind speed when excluding those hours and the fitting quality is slight lower. The average electricity price is a 10 % higher when the night and weekend hours are excluded. There are not important differences between the two graphs or analysis (see Figure 65).

Figure 65. Electricity Price in Portugal as a function of the wind speed, taking into account all hours (left) and excluding night and weekend hours (right). The vertical grey lines are the bar errors corresponding to each wind speed

The same test was repeated for different values of the maximum wind speed. The fitting results depend very little on the maximum wind speed, if the maximum wind speed is above 10 m/s.

Taking into account this information, two different types of models have been developed: Model A and Model B. If the wind speed is predicted to be w m/s at an instant of time t , then the predicted price of the electricity at that instant t will be:

$$\text{Model A: Average price } (w) \pm \sigma(w),$$

where $\sigma(w)$ is the standard deviation at w .

$$\text{Model B: Fit}(w) \pm \sigma(w),$$

where $\text{Fit}(w)$ is the function that fits the average electricity price and $\sigma(w)$ is the standard deviation at w ($\text{Fit}(w) = c_0 + c_1 * w + c_2 * w^2$).

These two models have been tested at some instants of times (November 2024) that were not in the database used to make the analysis and the models (see Figure 66).

Figure 66. Real and predicted electricity price at different hours and using the models

In Figure 66, Model A Average means Average Price(w), Model B Average means $\text{Fit}(w)$, Model A Highest means Average Price(w) + $\sigma(w)$ and Model B Highest means $\text{Fit}(w) + \sigma(w)$. According to the performed tests, any Model X Highest ($x=A$ or B) yields results similar to the real ones. Therefore, these models can be used by the quarry managers to make predictions of the electricity price based on the wind speed and to save electricity expenses. More tests are underway.

Data analysis for the production estimation model in Forecast service

The daily production at the CIMPOR quarry was compared with the daily weather conditions at weather stations close to the quarry. The correlations between production and four weather variables, during the period October 1st 2024 to February 26th 2025, were analysed: average relative humidity, average temperature, average wind speed and precipitation. The results are similar for the weather stations analysed. Only the results corresponding to the Santarem weather station have been plotted. They can be seen in Figure 67:

Figure 67. Production vs. the four mentioned weather variables at the Santarem weather station

As can be noticed in Figure 67, there is not a clear correlation between the production and the average wind speed, average relative humidity and average temperature. However, the production vs. precipitation plot shows that most of the production of the quarry took place during the days with zero precipitation. This result was expected and coherent with the conversations held with quarry operators, in which they explained how rain had the biggest impact in production. Even though for days with a higher precipitation the relationship between rain and production is not as clear, it was considered to move on with the model implementation assuming this relationship exists.

As regards the production vs the average wind speed, although there is not a clear correlation, it can be noticed that most of the production took place during a short interval of average wind speeds: 1.5 – 3 m/s.